

SOCIOLINGUISTIC PROFILE OF THE CONTEXT WHERE ENGLISH WILL BE USED

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The target group of students are currently admitted to secondary school in Andijan city. The students' English classroom context or instructions are aligned with the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). The national curriculum is designed by focusing more communicative skills which aim to prepare the language learners for real-life situations. School curriculum and yearly plans emphasize equipping the students with all academic background to be ready to transit for the next level of education, such as higher education, vocational collages, and international and local university admissions. The language program at school is developed to prepare the students for both local and international language testing examinations. The lessons are also structured to incorporate all four language skills. The English language classroom instructions are conducted in Uzbek, Russian and English in primary and secondary levels while the dominant classroom instruction language is English in high school level. Students usually apply all three language for their social interactions. However, for instructional context, Standard English varieties are preferred with limited revision of nonstandard English varieties. This leads to maintaining "neutral" or "prestigious" accents for communicative interactions. However, the students in this target local area are informed that the English language is taught to equip them with a conversational tool in international level. The language is not taught to express more power or authority by learning and applying a language in daily or professional contexts. The language cannot be used to judge or criticize one national identity over the other ones (Bayley & Villarreal, 2018). Over the course, the students are provided with opportunities to learn the language from authentic resources. By listening to podcasts, video vlogs, or watching Western media, the students have an opportunity to learn about Western culture and traditions. However, the national curriculum mentions the importance of preserving national identity while acquiring any foreign languages by eliminating feature that are not common to the national identity, such as applying gender-neutral language (Lankes,2022). As a result, course reading materials designed to combine cultural features of local community with the culture-specific features of foreign language. The language subordination is clearly observed in a target local area as the authority organizations do not dictate or discriminate language minorities in a target geographical area (Lippi-Green, 2004).

The English Language lessons are designed according to the National curriculum and limited to course reading textbooks. The selected textbooks do not consider some subgroups who obtain different level of language exposure. The educator should frequently modify and adapt the course reading textbooks to meet the needs of students with different levels of language proficiency. The educator should design and apply various types of formative and summative assessments to provide equal opportunities for the students with different abilities.

In regards of subgroup A, the educator should apply various methods of delivery to increase intrinsic motivation of the students. The educator can apply communication-based approaches that prioritize student's independence and collaboration. The methods such as CLT

and TBL can provide opportunities to design student-centered activities where they can practice not only the language units but also, they can develop their leadership and communicative skills. The application of digital tools for assessment and speaking practices may show the students purposeful utilization of devices in learning process. The educator can minimize code-switching and language mixing in the classroom by providing frequent feedback or by providing a chance for self-correction and self-evaluation. This practice allows the students to observe and notice code-switching and language mixing in their communication. To increase the involvement of parents in the process of L2 learning, the educator may organize practical workshops where they can observe and participate in a traditional language classroom. This practice allows the parents to observe their children in a real classroom practice and notice possible difficulties and challenges in L2 learning.

In regards of subgroup B, the educator should be creative in the process of designing lesson activities by preparing various visual aids, realia and infographics to ensure the materials be comprehended by the students. By organizing and grouping subgroup A students with subgroup B students in peer collaboration, the educator can increase student's self-confidence in communication. Implementing cultural aspects into learning process can increase student's involvement in learning process as they observe that their ethnical identity being respected (Deumert,2011).

In regards of gender and sexuality, the educator should form non-gendered groups where the students can be assigned into groups by the application of different colored cards or other digital tools such as spinning wheels for selecting mixed-gendered groups. Working in this groups enables the students to overcome their anxiety of collaborative tasks. To meet the needs of male students, the educator is advised to organize more movement-based tasks such as grammar marathons, funny starts where the revision of grammar unit is incorporated with sport game elements. It is important to design the lesson plans with more scaffolding for male students in writing and reading tasks to minimize the gap in academic performance of both genders. The educator should promote peer-evaluation and peer-discussions to improve female students' leadership skills.

In regards of race and ethnicity in the classroom, the educator should be very selective in the process of choosing a proper context for the classroom instructions. It would be more productive if the educator chose more neutral and international topics for classroom discussions. The educator can minimize the discomfort of the student from minor ethnic group by promoting activities that target the social awareness of dominant ethnic group cultural features. The educator should monitor and ensure that the Russian student is not left behind during the classroom activities. Additionally, the educator should be very sensitive in the process of noticing and addressing students' attitude toward language and language variations. The educator should not be too judgmental and critical if the certain accent features appear in students' oral communication. The case should be addressed by analyzing students prospective toward the language learning (Bayley & Villarreal, 2018). Moreover, the educator should track and reflect on his / her own attitude toward the language variations. Expressing negative attitude toward a certain accent can lead to the development of the same attitude by the students (Bayley & Villarreal, 2018).

The target group of students conduct both external and internal assessment over the academic year. As it was mentioned above, this group of students sit for international language

examinations, such as IELTS and SAT so the school curriculum contains practical lessons along with ongoing workshops that aim introducing specific skills for conducting these tests. The students have quarterly MOCK examinations (depending on their language proficiency level and age) that simulate real examination conditions. This practice is believed to reduce the level of stress and anxiety over the real examinations. Additionally, MOCK examination results are applied to tailor the instructional process to fill the gaps in teaching and learning.

As an internal assessment, the educators collect data of learning and for learning by administering formative and summative assessments over the academic year. These internal assessments are designed in the context of course reading appropriate to the students' age and language proficiency level. The calendar of assessment dates is introduced to both students and parents at the beginning of the academic year. The data collected is analyzed and shared over the departmental meetings which are aimed to modify or adapt curriculum to the needs of the students.

Designing and administering both formative and summative assessments is very challenging tasks. As the process of implementing and considering many specific aspects, such as gender bias, cultural and ethnical bias requires to be more selective to consider these features in every assessment paper. To minimize cultural bias in examinations, the national curriculum focuses on topics that are familiar to the students in all four skill assessments. To normalize gender equality, the assessment papers do not contain materials that prefer one gender over the another one.

Conclusion: In a language teaching and learning contexts, the educator plays an extremely important role. A case study of 14 affluent Uzbek and Russian students illustrated that teaching a language is not only about choosing proper curriculum or instructional concepts but also about developing sociolinguistic profile of the students. A language is systematic, dynamic, complex phenomenon that activity used in social context. (Bayley & Villarreal, 2018). The educator should not only consider "target culture", standards", "norms", "accent" while designing the course materials but also specific features of learners, such as age, gender, socioeconomical background, identity, ethnicity, race, attitude toward language variations. The research showed that these features may act as very important factors in materials selection, presentation and even evaluation. To have a very productive lesson, the educator should be aware of how to present the information, how much to present, when to present. To apply this in action, the educator should analyze and collect data about the sociolinguistic profile of the class.

In the classroom, the educator is responsible for creating safe and inclusive environment that simulates motivation and engagement in students toward a language learning. The lesson instructions should be free from criticism, and discrimination.

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